

GIS-based bedrock to soil element flux modelling: approach and limitations

Dörte Jordan^{a,b}, Laurens Kleijbeuker^b, Boy Weeland^b, Leo Kriegsman^a

^a Naturalis Biodiversity Centre, Dept. of Research & Education, Leiden

^b Utrecht University, Faculty of Geosciences, Dept. of Earth Sciences, Utrecht

The climate-driven, politically motivated green transition induces an increasing demand for critical metals and other so-called transition minerals needed to produce, store, and use renewable energy. Currently existing mines are unlikely to meet the steeply increasing demand in the coming years. Despite improved mining and extraction methods, new economic resources must be found.

We started two BSc projects, in the context of the EU-funded FluidNET ITN (Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956127), to test whether potential target areas for exploration can be found by recombining, interpolating, and re-interpreting existing geochemical data. Both projects combined national and international databases on bedrock, subsoil and topsoil geochemistry with GIS and various statistical approaches.

Despite recognizable correlations between the chemical composition of topsoil, subsoil, and bedrock, our study highlights the currently existing limitations of this approach. Firstly, despite data availability, accessibility was limited even when open access was advertised by, e.g., geological surveys and other databases. Secondly, available bedrock compositional data are restricted to specific rock types or areas, and soil data are widely spaced, resulting in poor coverage. These facts limit the reliability of larger scale interpolation. Thirdly, soil and bedrock samples are not analysed for the same set of elements, e.g., Si is usually missing in soil analysis. This hampers the direct comparison of datasets and complicates the interpretation, underscoring the importance of truly accessible and interoperable data. In conclusion, the preliminary results are promising, but clearly show gaps in sampling, analysis, and data curation.